

Kim Kneher, Marc Peterfi, Reinhold Hübl, David Obermayr: Using STACK to individualise tutorials in mathematics. In: Contributions to the International Meeting of the STACK Community 2023. TTK University of Applied Sciences: Tallinn, Estonia, 2023 1

Using STACK to individualise tutorials in mathematics

A case-study in the application of STACK to voluntary tutorials

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Abstract: The project EduFIT introduced a new digitally supported blended learning concept at the computer science department of the DHBW Mannheim where it aims to individualise tutorials and optimise practice time. This article shows how STACK questions were used to achieve this and what problems and learnings arose.

Keywords: Adaptive Feedback; Blended Learning; Formative E-Assessment; Self Regulated Learning

1 Setting

The Duale Hochschule Baden-Württemberg Mannheim² (DHBW Mannheim) is a university in Germany focussing on dual studies, which means that students alternate every three months between university and a partner company. ZeMath³ is responsible for the quality assurance of mathematical basic education at faculty of engineering e. g. by conducting mathematical pre-courses (Studienstart, cf. [We23b]), supporting organising and conducting mathematics courses and generating digital teaching materials and concepts for their use.

At the DHBW the assessment system STACK [Sa13], developed by Chris Sangwin for Moodle and adapted to ILIAS by Fred Neumann and Jesus Copado, has been used successfully for many years inside the trainings of the mathematical online pre-courses emerging from the opes project within the learning management system ILIAS (cf. [We21], [We19], [De21b]).

The positive experiences with digital questions as part of the pre-courses motivated an adaption of its use to the lectures. ILIAS is used only for the pre-courses, since the DHBW Mannheim uses Moodle as the learning management system for lectures. Therefore most of the questions used in the pre-courses could not be utilised in the lectures apart from STACK questions which are to some extent interchangeable between ILIAS and Moodle. We also used some questions from the database DOMAIN [AK23] run by AK Mathe Digital. By using external questions one should not underestimate the amount of time and effort

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needed to check this questions on correctness and to adapt them to the notation used in ones lectures. Therefore, we mostly created questions on ourselves, which are to be made available as open educational resources after quality assurance.

In a first small pilot run [We23a], online questions were used for hand-in-tasks in the summer semester 2022. They were used in three courses in the computer science departement in the lectures on calculus in first year's Mathematics I module. Since winter semester 2022, the use of STACK and other digital questions has been further explored and expanded as part of the project EduFIT⁴, which is funded by the *Stiftung Innovation in der Hochschullehre* as part of the *Freiraum 2022* program [St22].

The goal of EduFIT is to help students individually especially by picking up students at their individual learning level as well as to support tutorial teachers. Furthermore we want to detect and resolve common student errors and update the learning materials and questions based on this. Within the project, the concepts and contents where implemented for the calculus and linear algebra lectures within the first year of study in the courses of the computer science departement.

One has to take into account the general conditions of teaching at the DHBW. The students of computer sciences at the DHBW Mannheim are divided, regarding their specialisation, into individual courses with moderate group sizes of 20 to 30 students, with each course having their own lecturer. On the one hand, this means that the group sizes are already quite small. On the other hand, it places high demands on the coordination between the lecturers in the case of such a project, since content, notations and course procedure should be as congruent as possible if a pool of question and learning materials is to be used together. In the project we have five lecturers in six courses with about 170 students in total, six tutorial teachers and six student assistants.

The first year lectures were in the past usually supported by one voluntary weekly tutorial per course and the submission of assessed exercise sheets by the students. The exercise sheets usually contained four tasks that the students had to work on and submit within a week and which then were corrected by the lecturers and returned to the students. These exercise sheets were – albeit submitted digitally via the learning management system – classic exercise sheets that were worked on manually by students and corrected by their teachers. An automated evaluation of the student answers did not take place. In the first pre-project pilot some of the tasks were substituted by digital tests. The use of digital questions with direct evaluation places high demands on the quality and design of these questions to ensure that all students receive tasks of similar difficulty and that these problems are also being solved by the students themselves - without using electronic systems as help. In the time frame of the project, we therefore decided not to use the digital tasks as a one-to-one translation for hand in tasks, although this remains possible and interesting for future application. Instead we decided to concentrate on the use of feedback through digital questions.

⁴ acronym for *Einsatz digital unterstützter Fragen zur Individualisierung von Tutorien*; english: *using digitally supported questions to individualise tutorials*

In the EduFIT project the number of hand in tasks was reduced to three per exercise sheet and digital questions were used to optimise the tutorials emphasising their use in formative settings. We therefore mainly use STACK for formative testing, especially acknowledging the value of STACK for trainings using specific feedback. Nonetheless the possibility of giving partial credit and detecting special errors sets STACK as optimal for analysis of the group and suggesting special learning groups.

We used two types of tests in the project. One type were the *lecture tests* with summative settings in Moodle. These tests were short tests conducted after each lecture to detect the actual learning levels of the students and to allocate them to one of two tutorials based on their problems. In the first run they were due directly after each lecture. In the second run we changed them to occur bi-weekly and to be taken within a few days after the lecture. The test results are evaluated in two ways. On one hand, the courses are divided into two tutorials of approximately equal size per course based on the overall test results. On the other hand the students' answers and errors are also analysed in order to give the tutors information about weaknesses spotted in advance.

We also use *trainings* as another form of digital tests. These tests are completely formative and are used in the tutorials but can also be used by students for self study. The trainings are not only intended to support the students, but also the tutors, as they are used in the training units within the tutorials, which should enable the tutors to concentrate on the students who explicitly need their professional help, while the other students have already been helped sufficiently with the individual feedback, therefore optimising the tutorial time.

Fig. 1: Flowchart showing the use of tutorials and digital questions within a lecture week.

2 Some question examples

As we use STACK questions mostly for training purposes within the tutorials, we focus on questions which deliver a playful approach to certain concepts and/or give individual feedback to misconceptions or errors as well as model solutions, granting the student the opportunity to verify and elaborate their answers and the feedback [De21a]. For graphic inputs and outputs one can use the JSXGraph-library for JavaScript by the University of Bayreuth ([GVW10], [Va18]). For example figure 2 shows a question about ε - N -definition of sequence convergence which seems to be a common student problem to understand.

Fig. 2: Question regarding definition of convergence of a sequence using JSXGraph.

One can also use the plot options in STACK to generate static graphics which in the feedback can depend on the student answer as one sees in figure 3 where the newton polynomial and the student answer are sketched together with the interpolation points.

Even without graphical elements STACK allows to give feedback to common errors or misconceptions. Figure 4 shows a question about geometric series. Students are informed if they miss the individually set starting index of the summation but also if they falsely use the formula on a non-convergent series of a geometric type.

In basic set theory the question in figure 5 allows the students a relatively open input to a to some extent randomised question but can still give adaptive feedback on the mathematical properties of the answer and tell the students why their answer is not correct. In this case this is achieved by using feedback variables and question blocks and does not use a large potential response tree (PRT).

Most of the questions, except e. g. questions about algorithms, did not asked for interim results, since these would anticipate the calculation process. Subsequent errors, on the other hand, were handled e. g. by comparisons with results that occur in frequent student errors or error combinations. This of course requires an analysis of the most common mistakes made

Fig. 3: Question feedback about newton polynomial using generated static graphics

by students. The possibility, similar to the approach of [KG19], to start showing a stepped query of intermediate steps only if an incorrect solution is entered offers another promising prospect, but could not be addressed due to time constraints and technical reasons within the project to date.

3 Problems and possible solutions

The vast amount of topics to be covered in a single course and the even greater number of applications connected to said topics results in a large amount of possible question settings and tests we provide. Solely from a mathematical point of view, a range of about five to ten topics per week appears to be fitting to reflect the entirety of the topics in the tests. That results in about 50-100 tests or roughly 200-400 questions per semester, depending on the intensity in which they are used. That led to asking the question if this approach is motivating or even helpful for students.

As part of their student research project [HS23], two advanced students ran a survey in the six aforementioned courses. Said survey verified our assumption that most students tend to get tired by too many tests, a status we call 'overtesting'. As a result they get unsatisfied by their own results and the tests themselves thus disapproving of their use in general. That led to the conclusion not to run too many tests during one semester. At the same time the test results got worse over the course of one semester while less people participated in them despite the fact that they could gain bonus points for the final exam. All in all these observations led to the conclusion to choose the appropriate timing for supplemental tests and trainings since just releasing them too often causes overtesting.

The next problem in the daily use of STACK questions lies in developing them. Anyone who has created a larger number of questions had to use multiple variables at one point. Especially when giving specified and adaptive individual feedback, these blocks grow extensively. The underlying problem is the existence of so many possible errors the creator

Frage 1
Teilweise richtig
Erreichte Punkte 0,50 von 1,00

Überprüfen Sie die Reihe

$$\sum_{j=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j$$

auf Konvergenz und geben Sie ggf. den Wert der Reihe an.

$$\sum_{j=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j = \frac{1}{1-2/7}$$

Ihre letzte Antwort wurde folgendermaßen interpretiert:

$$\frac{1}{1 - \frac{2}{7}}$$

Geben Sie im Konvergenzfall den Reihenwert an. Schreiben Sie im Divergenzfall 1000 in das Antwortfeld.

Ihre Antwort ist teilweise korrekt.

Die gegebene geometrische Reihe konvergiert.
Wahrscheinlich haben Sie nicht beachtet, dass die Reihe nicht mit $j = 0$ startet, sondern mit $j = 3$.
Bei Ihrem Ergebnis $\frac{7}{5}$ berechnen Sie

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j.$$

Die Summanden mit Index kleiner $j = 3$ haben Sie zu viel dazu addiert. Sie müssen diese Summe

$$\sum_{j=0}^2 \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j = \frac{67}{49}$$

noch abziehen und erhalten dann

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j &= \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j - \sum_{j=0}^2 \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^j \\ &= \frac{7}{5} - \frac{67}{49} \\ &= \frac{8}{245}. \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 4: Question feedback to a question about a geometric series

has to cover and give feedback to or points for. Unfortunately this results in error prone questions.

While the students do not necessarily suffer from this, it greatly increases the amount of time a single person has to spend on one question in order for it to function properly. While the testing tools STACK provides help creating questions and testing if they work as intended, Moodle itself does not offer a debugging tool which makes the process of creation very hard, especially when using JSXGraphs. Since there are many errors not related to coding, such as overlooking a special case in the phrasing of a question or not anticipating a certain type of input the learning for us was to use STACK questions mostly for supporting purposes such as trainings and learning modules, while relying on exercise sheets and written exams for actual grading of students.

The focus point of our attention have to be the students and their acceptance of our methods. As the above mentioned survey showed, the discontent among students largely affected the acceptance of our methods. Though with good intention the questions were used carelessly and in the wrong places. Consequently the students opinion about the implementation of the basic math education was influenced in a negative way. The survey also showed multiple important aspects of the students view on our methods. As already mentioned the students

Geben Sie eine Teilmenge $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \{1, 2, 3\} \times \{1, 2, 3\}$ mit genau 2 Elementen so an, dass \mathcal{R} eine transitive Relation auf $\{1, 2, 3\}$ beschreibt. Tool zum Nachbessern der Frage | Frage-Tests und eingesetzte Varianten

$\mathcal{R} = \{([1,2],[2,3])\}$

Ihre letzte Antwort wurde folgendermaßen interpretiert:
 $\{[1, 2], [2, 3]\}$

Hinweis: Geben Sie Teilmengen von kartesischen Produkten in der Form $\{[1,2],[2,2],[2,3]\}$ an. Wichtig: Nutzen Sie eckige Klammern statt runder Klammern für die Tupel und verwenden Sie Kommata.

Ihre Antwort ist teilweise korrekt.
 Die von Ihnen angegebene Relation $\{[1, 2], [2, 3]\}$ umfasst genau 2 Elemente.
 Ihre angegebene Relation ist leider nicht transitiv.
 Da $(1, 2) \in \mathcal{R}$ und $(2, 3) \in \mathcal{R}$, aber $(1, 3) \notin \mathcal{R}$, ist Ihre Relation nicht transitiv.

Fig. 5: A question about transitivity of a relation with individual feedback

Fig. 6: student survey - run by advanced students during their thesis

did not necessarily enjoy the way the tests were implemented but they understood the use and supported the idea of giving extra materials to learn with. The idea of assigning them to different tutorials had to be put aside, since they would much rather choose their own tutorial. Since then we still hand out a recommendation which tutorial to attend but it is not mandatory.

We also adjusted the use of the tests and now call them trainings. Their purpose is still to give students an opportunity to apply knowledge they have accumulated during lectures but doing so is completely voluntary. At the same time we keep an open communication with the students about how grades are computed, how tests are used and how the tutorials are held, which was a big concern in free text input fields in the survey.

All of these problems raise the question if the amount of time and effort spend on special cases and feedback improvement is worth the price. The most important indicator a teacher can be interested in is the overall performance of their students, represented by their grades.

Alas, it is difficult to evaluate the actual impact of such a small part of a teaching approach. There are much bigger factors such as CoViD-19, their preexisting knowledge and the teachers themselves. We do know though, that online based pre-courses, greatly affect the growth in knowledge during the first semester and the overall grades students achieve [De21b]. Hence, the assumption that STACK based trainings are beneficial for the learning process is reasonable. Conclusively the answer to our question lies in the amount of time we can invest in creating the STACK based modules. As a first observation we want to state at this point that the initial creation of the questions for one course takes about one run of that course. In the next couple of runs the focus then shifts to maintaining and improving existing questions and therefore decreases over time.

Secondly, looking at travels through response trees we can identify problems students have in specific topics. The PRT in figure 7 was a first draft and definitely not optimal but the

Fig. 7: example of a potential response tree

lessons are the same nonetheless. Some nodes are almost never traversed in certain ways but still they are traversed. That means the questions cover some important feedback students might have needed to improve their knowledge in a certain topic. That being said the time and effort are almost always worth the price in our eyes, since helping students grow and learn mathematics was our intention in the first place.

Lastly we want to mention that creating STACK questions requires an understanding of STACK, Maxima, HTML and sometimes JavaScript when working with JSXGraph. We uncovered the use of good tutorials such as the ones by [ST23] as well as [Ka22] which should be just the beginning of a wide variety of video tutorials on STACK and how to deal with specific problems. At the same time the need of a database with multiple questions on various topics would greatly decrease the amount of time spent on developing questions and makes the existing community all the more valuable.

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